

Clinicopathological Study of Thyroid Masses in Tertiary Care Centre**Gujrathi Atishkumar¹, Paikrao Yogesh², Shende Neha³**¹Associate Professor, Dept. of ENT, Dr Shankarrao Chavan Government Medical College, Vishnupuri, Nanded, 431606, Maharashtra, India²Assistant Professor, Dept. of ENT, Dr Shankarrao Chavan Government Medical College, Vishnupuri, Nanded, 431606, Maharashtra, India.³Dr Shankarrao Chavan Government Medical College, Vishnupuri, Nanded, 431606, Maharashtra, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Thyroid swellings are very frequently encountered in ENT practice, ranging from a simple nodule to a malignant tumor. Disorder of structure of thyroid gland, due to various etiological factors, will give rise to swelling in the neck region. Clinical signs and symptoms are inadequate to diagnose thyroid disorders as similar presentations are seen in various thyroid disorders. So, this study of thyroid swellings was done to know different clinical presentations, age and sex distribution, correlation between thyroid swellings and thyroid function tests, analyze various thyroid swellings and etiological factors based on pathological reports.

Aims & Objectives: To study demographic profile of thyroid masses, To study symptomatology and clinical features of thyroid masses, To study correlation between clinical findings and pathological findings of the thyroid neck masses.

Methods & Materials: A prospective observational study conducted on patients attending the ENT opd, ipd and casualty of Dr SCGMC Nanded Govt medical college & hospital, from July 2022-January 2024. Patients with neck swellings between the age group of 11-70 years with thyroid swelling were in the inclusion criteria. The clinical presentations of patients were tabulated and analyses by descriptive statistics.

Results: A total number of 137 patients with neck swelling were evaluated. The incidence most common in 31-40 years, and most prevalent among females 65.7%, males being 34.3% most common clinical feature being neck swelling followed by symptoms of hyperthyroidism (7.2%), symptoms of hypothyroidism (3.6%), dysphagia (13.9%), change in voice (5.8%), cough (8.7%), and dyspnea (4.4%). Majority of the patients presented more than 6 months 2 years. Clinically majority of patients were Solitary thyroid nodule (35.8%) followed by Diffuse thyroid goiter (27.7%). Based on the FNAC results the most prevalent diagnosis had been colloid goitre (29.2%). Majority of specimens on HPE were diagnosed colloid goitre (21.9%).

Conclusion: In all cases of thyroid swellings, detailed clinical history, thorough clinical examination is required. Thyroid function test, USG and FNAC reports help to reach the definitive diagnosis. Histopathological report confirms and gives final diagnosis.

Keywords: Solitary thyroid nodule, MNG, colloid goitre.

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Introduction

The thyroid gland is a 10-20g, bilobed endocrine organ positioned midline in the anterior aspect of the neck. Thyroid disorders are developmental, inflammatory, hyperplastic, and neoplastic conditions of the thyroid that can result in structural enlargement of the organ, derangement of function, or both.

Disorders of the thyroid are among the most common endocrine diseases in humans. Thyroid masses commonly include thyroid lesions, solitary nodule, papillary carcinoma of thyroid, multinodular goiter, colloid goiter, lymphocytic thyroiditis, follicular neoplasm. Thyroid masses present commonly to clinicians. In the adult female popula-

tion, approximately 80 per cent of non-thyroid neck masses are neoplastic, and of these 80 per cent are metastatic, and in 75 per cent of these metastatic masses, the primary index tumors is located above the clavicle. In children under 15 years, 90 per cent of thyroid masses are benign and of these up to 55 per cent may be congenital.

Benign thyroid masses can be classified as congenital and acquired. The latter group are often enlarged lymphadenopathies, but there may be a wide range of different pathologies involved causing their swelling. Nutritional deficiencies, dietary goitrogens, viral, bacterial infections, autoimmune and physiological conditions are responsible for this

variety of lesions. Malignant lesions can present as primary as well as metastasis from various organs of the body. Neoplasms of neck region are a major form of cancer in India, accounting for 23% of all cancer in males and 6% in females. The disproportionately higher prevalence of malignancies in India may be due to use of tobacco in various forms, consumption of alcohol, low socioeconomic status related to poor hygiene, poor diet. The risk increases in proportion to the intensity & duration of the exposure to each causative agent.

The evaluation and management of patients who present with a neck lump, should have a systematic and uncompromising clinical approach using the history, physical examination internal and external neck examination, followed by relevant investigations, which may include bloods tests, radiological studies, Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and biopsy.

Purpose of this study is to evaluate the clinicopathological of thyroid masses with demographic and clinical profiles of the patients presenting in the out-patient department and in-patient department of ENT, in this tertiary care hospital by different investigating modalities and to correlate the clinical aspects with pathological reports.

The study of thyroid masses can be justified by the fact that thyroid masses are of significant importance because of the anatomical location of the 3 masses which can compromise the airway compressing the trachea, can obstruct the food pathway causing difficulty in deglutition. Hence the study of

thyroid masses is of much importance.

Materials & Methods: A prospective observational study conducted on patients attending the ENT opd, ipd and casualty of Dr SCGMC Nanded Govt medical college & hospital, from July 2022-January 2024. Patients with neck swellings between the age group of 11-70 years with thyroid swelling were in the inclusion criteria.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Any patient who does not give consent to be the part of the study.
- Patients who denies participation after giving written informed consent.

All the patients presenting with thyroid swellings were subjected to thorough history to know the onset, duration and progression of thyroid swellings.

Then they were clinically examined by inspection, palpation (by Pizzillo's,) & auscultation. The patients underwent THYROID FUNCTION TEST in the form of free T3, free T4 and ultra TSH in serum.

All the patients were subjected to ultrasonography of neck which gave the information about the size, extent, vascularity, echotexture, calcification, consistency (solid/cystic), laterality of thyroid swelling. They underwent fine needle aspiration cytological examination, after surgery the sample was sent for HPE.

Result & Observation:

Table 1: Distribution of Study Population on the basis of Symptoms

Symptoms	Frequency	Percent
Swelling over neck	137	100.0
Symptoms of Hyperthyroidism	10	7.2
Symptoms of Hypothyroidism	5	3.6
Dyspnea	6	4.4
Change in Voice	8	5.8
Dysphagia	19	13.9
Cough	12	8.7

Table 2: Distribution of Study Population on the basis of Clinical Diagnosis

Clinical diagnosis	Frequency	Percent
Colloid cyst	35	25.5
Diffuse thyroid goiter	38	27.7
Multinodular goiter	15	10.9
Solitary thyroid nodule	49	35.8
Total	137	100.0

Table 3: Distribution of Study Population based on FNAC Diagnosis

FNAC	Frequency	Percent
Colloid goiter	40	29.2
Diffuse thyroid goiter	18	13.1
Multinodular goitre	24	17.5
Follicular neoplasm	18	13.1
Adenomatous goiter	19	13.8

HashimotosThyroiditis	18	13.1
Total	137	100.0

Table 4: Distribution of Study Population on the basis of Histopathology

HPE	Frequency	Percent
Colloid goiter	30	21.9
Colloid goiter with Cystic change	10	7.3
Adenomatous goiter	20	14.6
Hashimotos thyroiditis	12	8.8
Multinodular goiter	25	18.24
Follicular adenoma	16	11.7
Papillary carcinoma of Thyroid	24	17.5
Total	137	100.0

Table 5: Distribution of Study Population on the basis of Thyroid function test

Thyroid Status	Frequency	Percent
Euthyroid	130	94.8
Hyperthyroid	4	2.9
Hypothyroid	3	2.1
Total	137	100.0

Figure 1: Distribution of Study Population

Figure 2: Right lobe Colloid Goitre on the basis of Symptoms

Figure 3: Distribution of Study Population on the basis of Clinical Diagnosis

Figure 4: Multinodular goitre

Figure 5: Distribution of Study Population based on FNAC

Figure 6: Specimen of multinodular goitre

Figure 7: Histology of MNG

Figure 8: Histology of colloid goitre

Discussion:

- There were 34.3% males and 65.7% females in the study with male to female ratio of (1.9:1).
- Majority of the patients with thyroid mass were belong to age group between 31-40 years (47%). Minimum age of the patient was 20 years and maximum age was 67 years.
- Around 50% out of 137 patients belonged to lower socio-economic status.
- All the 137 patients had presented with a complaint of swelling over the neck as the primary complaint along with symptoms of hyperthyroidism (7.2%), symptoms of hypothyroidism (3.6%), dysphagia (13.9%), and change in voice (5.8%), cough (8.7%), and dyspnea (4.4%).
- Majority of the patients presented more than 6 months to after the presentation of swelling over neck for the first time.
- 130 patients presented in euthyroid state (94.8%), 4 presented with hyperthyroid state (2.9%) & 3 presented with hypothyroid state (2.1%).
- Clinically majority of patients were Solitary thyroid nodule (35.8%) followed by Diffuse thyroid goiter (27.7%), colloid cyst (25.5%) and Multinodular Goiter (10.9%).
- Based on the FNAC results the most prevalent diagnosis had been colloid goitre (29.2%), diffuse thyroid goiter (13.1%), follicular neoplasm (13.1%), 127 Hashimoto's thyroiditis (13.1%), adenomatous goitre (13.8%), and multinodular goitre (17.5%).

Majority of specimens on HPE were diagnosed colloid goitre (21.9%), goitre (21.9%), and papillary carcinoma of thyroid (17.5%), adenomatous goitre (14.6%) multinodular goitre (18.24%), follicular adenoma (11.7%), and Hashimoto's thyroiditis (8.8%), colloid goitre with cystic changes (7.3%). 9. Considering histopathology as the gold standard, most common cause for thyroid mass was of benign etiology (64.3%) and malignant etiology (35.7%).

Conclusion:

Neck mass is a frequently encountered problem in all age groups. It requires detailed history and clinical examination to arrive at an etiology.

Detailed investigations including THYROID FUNCTION TEST, USG neck, FNAC of the neck mass has to be done after a detailed clinical examination. CT scan and MRI was done in relevant cases.

In this study the most common thyroid masses most commonly benign masses like Solitary thyroid nodule (35.8%) most commonly presented between the age group 31-40 years. Colloid nodule remains the second most common cause on the

basis of clinical examination. Proper clinical examination with support of USG and fine needle aspiration cytology offers a simple method of diagnosis of neoplastic and nonneoplastic lesions in the neck. FNAC can be performed as an outpatient procedure without complications. The procedure is acceptable to most of the patients. There is no need for anesthesia and results can be made available within short duration of time. Fine needle aspiration cytology of neck masses with clinical correlation can provide most useful information to surgeon to determine the further mode of management and also serves as a complementary procedure for histopathological examination. However confirmatory and accurate diagnosis is given by histopathology.

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